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e-ABSTRACT BOOK

CLIMATE CHANGE AND IRRIGATION STRATEGIES: EFFECTS ON FUNGAL PATHOGENS IN MAIZE CULTIVATION

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Maize is a primary crop for agricultural production and export in the Republic of Serbia. However, despite the region's suitability for maize cultivation, production is often hindered by the presence of mycotoxigenic fungi, genera *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus*, and *Penicillium* are the most common. The occurrence of pathogens leads to reduced yield, quality of seed, and can also cause indirect damage in livestock production. After pathogen infection, maize kernels can become contaminated with mycotoxins. These compounds are harmful to humans and animals. In recent years, there has been particular attention to the presence of mycotoxins in food. Climate change and conditions that favor the emergence of pathogens require the implementation of various measures to create more favorable conditions for plant growth. Consequently, by enhancing plant resistance under adverse conditions, the pressure from pathogens can be reduced. The aim of this experiment was to determine whether the application of irrigation affects the reduction of ear rot. The study is conducted at two locations: Ravno Selo and Kovilj during the year 2024. Field disease assessment for ear rot involved the evaluation of a total of 60 plants in each treatment at the harvest phenological stage. Within each treatment replication, ears from inner rows were visually inspected using the seven-class disease severity scale established by Reid et al. (1996): 1 - 0%, 2 – 1-3%, 3 - 4-10%, 4 – 11-25%, 5 – 26-50%, 6 – 51-75%, and 7 – 76-100% of kernels exhibiting rot symptoms. The Disease severity index (DSI) in the field was determined using the Townsend-Heuberger formula. Characteristic symptoms of ear rot were observed, and disease rating was conducted. At the Ravno Selo locality recorded DSI was 8.15% for the irrigated plot and 16.67% for the non-irrigated plot. At the Kovilj locality, DSI was 8.89% for the irrigated plot and 15.19% for the non-irrigated plot.

Keywords: maize, irrigation, mycotoxigenic fungi, mycotoxins

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